

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Development of SiC nano-particle/Mg₂Si thermoelectric composites

Junki Nakano^{1*}, Yutaro Arai¹, Ryo Inoue¹, Tsutomu Iida¹, and Yasuo Kogo¹

¹ Department of Material Science & Engineering, Tokyo University of Science

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Introduction of Thermoelectric materials Mg₂Si

Abundant resources, Low density, High power generation around automotive exhaust gas temperature, Low toughness ~0.64 MPa·m^{1/2}

Figure of merit, ZT

$$ZT = \frac{S^2 \sigma}{K} T$$

S: Seebeck coefficient $S = \Delta V / \Delta T$
 σ : Electrical conductivity
 K : Thermal conductivity, $T: (T_H + T_L) / 2$

Fig. Schematic of thermoelectric power generation^[1].

Fig. Relationship between temperature and figure of merit, ZT of various thermoelectric materials.

Fig. Applications of automotive thermoelectric generator.

Improvement of fracture toughness is necessary.

[1] G.J.SNYDER et al., *Nature mat.*, **7**, 105-114, (2008). [2] M.G.Kanatzidis et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, **48**, 8616-8639, (2009)
 [3] J. Zhao et al., *J. Mater. Chem. A*, **3**, 19774-19782, (2015). [4] A.J.Minnich et al, *Energy Environ. Sci.*, **2**, 466-479, (2009).
 [5] G.Chen et al., *International Materials Reviews*, **48**, 45-66, (2003).

Toughening of Mg₂Si and its problems

Particle dispersed composites

Fig. Schematic of barrier height of intragranular composites and intergranular composites.

Reinforcement must be dispersed within grains.

Fig. Relationship between normalized toughness, K_c/K_c^m , and normalized ZT, ZT^c/ZT^m , at 873K.

Improvement of toughness without reducing TE properties is important.

Results and discussion : Mechanical properties

Fig. The relationship between SiC content and fracture toughness and typical crack paths in Pure Mg₂Si and Mg₂Si-SiC10vol%

SiC nano-particle deflects crack propagation.

Results and discussion : Thermoelectric and Mechanical properties

Fig. Temperature dependence of Electrical conductivity and Hall mobility.

Fig. Relationship between normalized toughness, K_c^c / K_c^m , and normalized ZT, ZT^c / ZT^m , at 873K.

Conclusions

- Intragranular composites with SiC nano-particles incorporated within Mg₂Si grains were successfully fabricated by using SiC nano-particle incorporated Mg₂Si granules.
- The fracture toughness of the intragranular composites increased as the SiC nano-particle content increased. It was reached 1.15 MPa · m^{1/2}, which is 1.80 times larger than Pure Mg₂Si and the main toughening mechanism were crack deflection.
- Incorporating reinforcement within the Mg₂Si particles proved an effective way to improve toughness without reducing TE properties when adding a reinforcing phase compared with intergranular composites.
- Even if relatively high amount of reinforcement is introduced into Mg₂Si, the improvement of fracture toughness without reducing ZT is realized by intragranular reinforcement.